

Viscosity *B*-Coefficients of some Known Drug Molecules (as Hydrochlorides) at 298 K

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Manuscript received 21 September 1993, revised 6 April 1994, accepted 29 April 1994

Viscosity *B*-coefficients of a number of drugs, viz. hydrochlorides of promethazine, chlorpromazine, papaverine, ephedrine, pseudoephedrine and isoxsuprine, in water have been determined, and found to be fairly high. The solvation numbers, single ion viscosity *B*-coefficients (B_+) show that the cations of promethazine, chlorpromazine and papaverine are highly solvated due to hydrophobic hydrations whereas other cations are relatively less solvated.

Viscosity is one of the important tools for the determination of ion-solvent interactions which are the controlling forces in dilute solutions where ion-ion interactions are absent^{1,2}. The structures of the solvents and solutes are significantly modified in solutions causing wide variations in their properties. The viscosity *B*-coefficient of an electrolyte actually represents the ion-solvent interaction parameter conditioned by the ion-size and solvent. *B*-coefficients of electrolytes, however, cannot give any impression regarding ion-solvent interactions unless they are separated into ionic *B*-components. The *B*-coefficients of ions usually give some idea regarding the modification of the solvent structure by the ions.

The physiological behaviour of structurally non-specific drugs are dependent on certain physicochemical properties, like ionisation, solubility, polarisability, surface properties, hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interactions etc. and are related to the thermodynamic activities of the drugs in solution^{3,4}. The study of the viscosity *B*-coefficients are particularly relevant as the pharmacologic response are determined by the structural variations of the drug molecules in solution. In order to have proper correlation of the different physicochemical properties of the drugs with their pharmacologic behaviour, we considered it useful to compile the viscosity coefficients of drugs at 298 K. These have led us to determine the viscosity of some of the drug molecules at our disposal. The results are presented in this communication.

Results and Discussion

The Jones-Dole equation⁵ has been used to analyse the relative viscosities of electrolytes,

$$(\eta/\eta_0 - 1) / \sqrt{C} = A + B \sqrt{C} \quad (1)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and water respectively, and C is the molar concentration. The other terms have their usual significance. Due to solubility limitations, the concentrations in most cases are usually in the range 0.01–0.10 *M*. However, the highly soluble promethazine hydrochloride shows gradual change in colour with time.

The plots of $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ against \sqrt{C} for the electrolytes are found to be linear without scatter. The A and B values, calculated using the least-square method, have been given in Table 1. The regression coefficient values are also given in Table 1. A -values have been found to be negative in general. However, A -values have been calculated theoretically using the Falkenhagen-Vernon⁶ equation,

$$A_{\text{theor}} = \frac{0.2577}{\eta_0 (\epsilon T)^{1/2} \lambda_+^0 \lambda_-^0} \left[1 - 0.6863 \left(\frac{\lambda_+^0 - \lambda_-^0}{A^0} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

The λ_+^0 values have been obtained from the A^0 -values of the drugs determined previously in our laboratory⁷ and the $\lambda^0(\text{Cl}^-)$ values⁸ obtained from the literature. The theoretically calculated A -values are given in parenthesis (Table 1). As expected, A -values for the salts decrease in order of increasing B -values. In the absence of temperature coefficient data, it is difficult to say positively from the B -values whether the molecules are structure-makers or structure-breakers in water. But most of the drugs have hydrophobic groups, and structural stabilisation due to hydrophobic interactions should lead to high positive values of B . Moreover, B -values may increase with increase in size of the drug molecules. In general, antihistaminic drugs have high B -values. However, it is premature to correlate B -values with their drug activities. For a better understand-

ing of the nature of the ion-solvent interactions, the ionic B_+ values have been determined using B_{Cl^-} values obtained based on the assumptions, $B_{\text{K}^+} = B_{\text{Cl}^-}$ ⁹ and $B_{\text{CS}^+} = B_{\text{I}^-}$ ¹⁰. The differences in B_+ values of the drug cations (Table 1) obtained from the two methods are very small. The values are positive and the higher values of B_+ indicate greater structure formation of water around the drug molecules. But the structure formation is likely to be lowered by the presence of OH groups.

The biological response of the drug⁴ can be written as¹⁰

$$\text{biological response} = f(\text{hydrophobic parameters}) + f(\text{electronic parameters}) + f(\text{steric parameters}) + f(x) + e \quad (3)$$

x represents one or more functions such as hydrogen bonding or polarisability and e is the correction factor. Similarly, B^+ can be dissected as^{1,11}

$$B^+ = B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Einst}} + B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Orient}} + B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Str}} + B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{reinf}} \quad (4)$$

$B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Einst}}$ is the positive increment arising from the obstruction to the viscous flow of the solvent caused by the shape and size of ions, the greater size obviously indicates greater $B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Einst}}$. $B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Orient}}$ and $B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Str}}$ are the contributions to viscosity arising from the enhance-

TABLE 1 - VISCOSITY A , B COEFFICIENTS, B_+ COEFFICIENTS AND SOLVATION NUMBERS OF THE CATIONS OF THE DRUG MOLECULES

Sl no.	Drug as hydrochlorides	A (A_{Theor})	B	Regression coefficient (γ)	B_+ -values of cations based on		Approximate solvation number (n_s)
					$B_{\text{CS}^+} = B_{\text{I}^-}$	$B_{\text{K}^+} = B_{\text{Cl}^-}$	
1	Promethazine	-0.006 (0.008)	1.420	0.99	1.417	1.427	25
2.	Chlorpromazine	-0.102 (0.008)	2.199	0.98	2.196	2.206	43
3	Papaverine	-0.108 (0.008)	2.240	0.98	2.237	2.247	44
4	Ephedrine	0.043 (0.008)	0.703	0.98	0.700	0.710	11
5.	Pseudoephedrine	0.049 (0.008)	0.661	0.99	0.658	0.668	12
6	Isoxsuprine	0.064 (0.008)	0.598	1.01	0.595	0.605	5

ment or destruction of the solvent structure by the ion causing increase or decrease in viscosity. $B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{reinf}}$ is the positive increment conditioned by the enhancement of the water structure by the molecular cations due to hydrophobic hydration. This appears to be the limiting factor and is related to f (hydrophobic response). Separation of these terms has not been possible even in case of simple ions. For all the cations, hydrophobic interaction (i.e. B^{reinf}) is predominant but it is least for isoxsuprinium ion due to possible effect of OH groups. For ephedrine and pseudoephedrine, the difference in B_+ is due to $B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Orient}}$. But for promethazinium and chlorpromazinium ions, the difference in B_+ is due to B_+^{Str} . B_+^{reinf} appears to be greatest for these ions and papaverinium ion.

The B_+ coefficient can be quantitatively treated by the Einstein equation¹². Thus, we have

$$B_{\text{ion}} = 2.5\bar{V} = 2.5 \times 4 \frac{R_{\pm}^3 N}{1000} \quad (5)$$

assuming that the ion behaves as rigid sphere with an effective radius R_{\pm} moving in a continuum. In view of solvation of ions, R_{\pm} value is generally greater than crystallographic radius of the ion. The number n_s of solvent molecules bound to the ion in the primary solvation shall can be calculated combining the Jones-Dole equation with Einstein's¹³,

$$B_{\text{ion}} = \frac{2.5}{1000} (V_1 + \eta_s V_s) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where, } B_{\text{ion}}^{\text{Einst}} = \frac{2.5}{1000} V_1 = \frac{2.5}{1000} \times \frac{4}{3} \pi r_1^3 N \quad (7)$$

V_1 and r_1 are the molar volume and crystallographic radius of the ion respectively.

An approximate idea regarding the solvation number of ions can be obtained taking the radii values of some of these ions from the conductivity data reported previously by us⁷. Approximate values of the solvation numbers are given in Table 1. It can be said that cations of promethazine, chlorpromazine and papaverine are hydrated to a greater extent due to hydrophobic hydration while those of ephedrine, pseudoephedrine and isoxsuprine are less hydrated. For quantification, correct radii values are needed.

Experimental

The drugs used were hydrochlorides of promethazine (mol. wt. 320.5), chlorpromethazine (355.5), papaverine (375.84), ephedrine (210.8 with 1/2 H₂O), pseudoephedrine (201.8) and isoxsuprine (537.9). The drugs were purified as described earlier⁵.

The densities of the experimental solutions were measured with a precision of 0.01% with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer (25 ml) calibrated with distilled water. The densities ρ of the working solutions were obtained from the relation¹⁴,

$$\rho = \rho_o + \theta m \quad (8)$$

where m is the concentration (mol dm⁻³) of solutions, ρ_o the solvent density and θ an empirical constant determined by density measurement on the most concentrated solution studied for each salt. The experimental densities agreed well with those calculated using the above equation.

The kinematic viscosity of each solution was measured using two suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer with a flow time of 150.3 (I) and 320.2 s (II) for distilled water at 298 K. The viscometers were calibrated from the average flow time (t) and densities of triple-distilled water at three different temperatures. The following equation was used for this purpose,

$$\eta/\rho = Kt - \frac{L}{t} \quad (9)$$

where η is the absolute viscosity of water. The absolute viscosities of water were taken from the literature. The characteristic constants K and L of the viscometer were respectively found to be 6.0821×10^{-5} and 2.50228×10^{-2} for (I) and 3.1301×10^{-5} and 2.2777×10^{-1} for (II). The calibration of the viscometer was periodically checked by measuring the flow times with water at three temperatures and the ratio of K/L of the viscometer constant was found to be constant during the course of the work. Runs were repeated until three successive determinations were obtained within 0.1 s. Corrections for kinetic energy were not made. The estimated precision of the viscosity measurements was $\pm 0.05\%$.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Mr. B. Mondal, Deputy Director, Central Drug Laboratory, Calcutta, for supplying the drugs. One of the authors (A.K.B.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi, for a Senior Research Fellowship.

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